

SIM4RDM project report outline

SIM4RDM is a two year project funded under the Seventh Framework Programme. The project aims to enable researchers to effectively utilise emerging data infrastructures by ensuring that they have the knowledge, skills and support infrastructures necessary to adopt good research data management methodologies.

Landscape study

The landscape study aimed to establish which interventions are used by funding agencies, research institutions, national infrastructure bodies and publishers across Europe to improve the capacity and skills of researchers in making effective use of research data infrastructures. Based on the target areas identified in the Jisc Managing Research Data Programme, and further desk research, an online survey was conducted, to which 18 national infrastructure providers, 20 research funders, 107 research institutions and 7 publishers responded. The findings of the survey and desk research were presented and feedback was collected in a workshop attended by 23 participants from across all stakeholder groups. 12 researchers were interviewed to validate the results identified previously.

Various national infrastructure bodies have been established to coordinate research data management activities, such as access to tools and materials, in order to establish long-term preservation and sharing practices, assist in the policies of research funders, and create infrastructures. Most of these national bodies are funded by the government, often in a project format. National bodies could take the lead in draft a national code of conduct which encourages the creation and use of data management plans. They should also suggest and supply appropriate tooling and adapt that to the national context. Furthermore they should take an active role in data citation practices.

Interviews with researchers indicate that the main drivers for writing a data management plan are requirements by the funder or the publisher. Nearly half of the research funders who took part in the survey have a policy covering research data management, whilst a quarter of the funders require data management plans as part of the grand application. Data management plans should address data acquisition, use, re-use, storage and protection and the rights of ownership. Just over one third of the responding funding organisations designate a specific organisation for preservation, although no term has been identified.

Funding bodies should encourage researchers by offering clear instructions to create a data management plan at the level of the project proposal. Call funds should be allocated to research data management. Funders can designate centres to store research data.

For publishers, policies have yet to become established instruments. Policies that do exist require readers and reviewers to provide links to the data underlying the article. In some cases publishers also require them to make available entire datasets when submitting the article, but not to keep them up to date. Publishers generally do not employ standards for data. Digital object identifiers are indeed used for citing, but data are cited in different ways. A dialogue should be established with publishers and publishers' associations about the definition of data policies. Possible elements are persistent identifiers for citation of data and requirements of trustworthiness for repositories in which data are to be deposited.

The number of research institutions with a policy is growing. Of those without a policy 42% intend to do define a policy in the next year. The main driver for the creation is the requirement by funders or a national code of conduct. For institutions without a policy academic demand or general commitment to open access can drive the establishment of a data management plan. 15% the research institutions that have responded to the survey actually prescribe a data management plan. 50% of the responding organisations offer an infrastructure for storage, management and access for research data made up by a variety of file storage and library systems. Research institutions should develop policies which contain elements that support scholars and scientists in their management.

Interviews with researchers show that policies should primarily cover roles and responsibilities for managing data, mechanisms for storage, backup, registration, deposit and retention of research data, access to re-use of data, open accessibility and availability of data and long term preservation and curation. They should also address data infrastructures and create workflows for data publishing and archiving. In addition such policies can bridge the gap between data and publication by crediting researchers for publishing research data. Researchers indicated they would significantly benefit from face-to-face support and training, but were found to consider flyers, meetings, seminars and presentations not very effective.

The setting for research data management is broader than initially anticipated. Other stakeholders need to be brought in as well, e.g. editorial boards of scientific journals, data centres and infrastructure providers. Research societies may intervene with the development of common practices. Infrastructure providers could intervene with common data formats for preservation and storage, tools and utilities. Policies from funders, institutes and editorial boards may influence researchers to use the principle of ‘share and share alike’.

Funding framework

Landscape study findings showed that the European RDM landscape is complex, with huge variation of maturity levels and stakeholders tending to work in isolation from each other. The project's initial view of the RDM landscape focused on researchers, their institutions, research funders and national infrastructure providers. It gradually became apparent that the picture is wider, with research publishers, independent infrastructure providers, non-governmental funders and professional associations also playing a part.

To address this complex RDM landscape a so-called 'core-plugin' model was devised. The 'core' part refers to the most basic common RDM issues likely to be encountered across Europe, while the 'plug-in' element covers the medium and more advanced RDM issues that vary across countries and stakeholders. This model builds on previous work by various organizations and projects, including Jisc, UKOLN, DCC, ANDS etc, to which it adds its own cross-cultural/ cross-stakeholder dimension, in line with the project's vision and findings of the Landscape study. The original aim of helping funders design and evaluate RDM interventions is thus expanded to include activities other stakeholders can do to increase the effectiveness of RDM policies and improve RDM awareness and practice across Europe and beyond.

In line with previous work carried out in this field, five areas were identified as critical for RDM: organizational, legal, technical, user experience, and data reuse. A number of frequently reported RDM barriers and enablers were analysed, and “target lists” highlighting the features of an ideal fully mature RDM landscape were created. From these target lists, a series of step-by-step actions for each stakeholder group were drawn, to help them move towards higher RDM maturity. These series of step-by-step activities were grouped together in the so-called RDM “cookbook”. Each

cookbook entry was referenced according to its intended stakeholder, RDM area, and maturity level, to allow for consistent cross-referencing with the Evaluation Framework. The cookbook was subject to a number of iterations based on feedback collected in project workshops and case studies.

In order that this framework for improving RDM becomes effective, it needs a complementary Evaluation framework to allow stakeholders self-assess their maturity and measure progress. A typical process for increasing RDM maturity involves a number of steps, as detailed below.

Stakeholders assess their RDM maturity using an evaluation tool that can be tailored to their needs. The maturity levels acquired in various RDM areas can then be visualised on multi-axis diagrams to help users identify the areas they would like to improve. Self-assessment results also trigger related “cookbook” entries that suggest step-by-step activities to increase maturity. To help users implement these activities, RDM best practice, information and tools are made available in the framework's knowledge base, and user experience is showcased in case studies from across Europe. Having decided what RDM aspects they want to improve, users complete the suggested activities, re-assess themselves and compare new levels with initial ones. The cycle can be reiterated to reach higher maturity. User feedback on the effectiveness of the framework is gathered in new case studies aimed at improving the framework and boost RDM collaboration.

Evaluation Framework

The purpose of the evaluation framework was to build an effective and flexible model for assessing RDM maturity across Europe using a simple easy to follow process. Work started with identifying the main motivations and driving forces animating the stakeholder groups surveyed in the landscape study. While closely related, these groups are still very different from each other, with different approaches to, and expectations from, RDM. A common frame of reference is needed to evaluate RDM maturity and progress for all players, but flexible enough to address users' specific needs.

A model highlighting the relationships within and beyond the RDM ecosystem was produced. Based on this model, and with input from the Landscape study and Funding Framework, an Evaluation Framework was conceived, with the following characteristics:

- Ecosystem-oriented: designed to address both common and specific needs of main stakeholder groups
- Dynamic: aimed for users at various maturity levels and RDM implementation stages;
- User-customisable: allows new assessment criteria and investigation areas to be added without affecting overall evaluation process;
- Benchmarked: provides both absolute and relative results, to allow positioning against previous users;
- Hybrid: allows for a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessment;
- Modular: structured on five RDM areas (organizational, technical, legal, user engagement, data reuse);
- Hierarchical: structured on 3 maturity levels (baseline, intermediate, advanced);
- Relational: consistent referencing across questionnaire and cookbook to allow each question to be linked with a cookbook activity
- Cross-correlated: allows identifying trends and commonalities within and across stakeholder groups.

In correlation with the Funding Framework cookbook, five questionnaires were created, one for each stakeholder group. Each questionnaire covers five RDM areas (organizational, technical, legal, user engagement, data reuse), and each question provides six answers at three complexity levels to choose from (2 baseline, 2 intermediate, 2 advanced), with gradual maturity increments from 1 to 6. Based on the users' answers, an absolute and a benchmarked score are provided, and step-by-step recommendations for improving RDM practice are suggested. The questionnaires were updated with feedback collected in a number of project workshops and case studies.

Case studies

The aim of the case studies work package was to test and improve the SIM4RDM Funding and Evaluation frameworks. The work was carried out with help from stakeholders in four European countries, who self-assessed their maturity and provided feedback for future improvement.

Lorraine Earth and Environment Observatory (OTELo) /Institute for scientific and technical information (INIST-CNRS)

OTELo is a group of four research units from different French research institutions who have established a partnership with a scientific and technical information support unit, INIST-CNRS. Together with promoting RDM at local and national levels, the main aim of this case study was to use the SIM4RDM frameworks to explore how social infrastructure (INIST) can help institutions and researchers coordinate their actions to improve RDM maturity and practice.

The focus was on the organizational and technical aspects of RDM. Initially a group of 15 OTELo professionals engaged in strategic reflection on data management, preservation and sharing took part in testing the SIM4RDM tool. The survey was conducted sequentially with an increasing number of respondents up to 29.

The survey indicated a low level of the overall RDM maturity level – less than 1 on a scale of 8. The little RDM awareness and lack of appropriate incentives for OTELo researchers was confirmed by respondents' input. The other staff surveyed also showed variable levels of knowledge and skills

in this domain, which confirmed the lack of appropriate RDM personnel, technical infrastructure and tools. The assessment revealed that the most valuable suggested actions for improving RDM practice were at baseline level. These included identifying and publishing relevant information and best practices on DM standards and data sharing, and depositing datasets and linking them to publications locally and internationally. Monitoring and publishing relevant RDM information were also essential.

Overall OTELo and INIST were satisfied with their participation in the SIM4RDM case study. The questionnaire helped them get an overview of their RDM maturity and identify their own local issues. Having assessed the results, they started implementing some of the recommended actions. The SIM4RDM frameworks were considered very useful for getting started with RDM. The vocabulary was quite specific and sometimes not easy to understand. Other suggestions for improving the questionnaire was to provide a clearer sense of increased maturity level from one answer to another. Pointing to available resources and use cases would also improve the effectiveness of the framework. It was suggested that the sustainability of the tool would be increased by adopting a Memorandum of Understanding by all parties involved, and identifying effective incentives for all stakeholders.

VU University Amsterdam/Department of Communication Science, Faculty of Social Sciences
The Department of Communication Science at VU University Amsterdam plans to develop an openly accessible online platform for social science research to facilitate research workflows within the scientific field. This platform will increase the transparency and reproducibility of research, and contribute to cumulative knowledge building. The success of the platform depends on the critical mass of future users; therefore it is extremely important to identify the features most likely to boost user engagement. The case study used the SIM4RDM frameworks to identify critical factors for user engagement, hence making the future platform more effective.

Researchers were the main target of this case study. The most relevant areas for testing were organizational, legal, technical and user engagement, especially on topics like management policy and support, data access, depositing datasets, and sustainability. In order to meet the goals of this study, the questionnaire was made more concise and less detailed. 539 respondents with a wide global spread contributed, with an overall RDM maturity level of 2 out of 8.

The feedback confirmed that most researchers see the need for adequate RDM provision, but they are more likely to comply with requirements when effective RDM infrastructure and incentives are in place. Institutions and journals are the least mature in setting RDM requirements, and institutions are also underdeveloped in providing RDM-related technical and legal support. The major bottleneck is the lack of incentives and requirements contributing with good RDM practices, especially among funding agencies, research institutions and publishers. This impacts directly on the researchers, therefore these institutional actors need to collaborate in developing sustainable RDM practices. Another important point was that in order to effectively tackle legal and ethical issues associated with user engagement, various stakeholder groups worldwide need to be involved in designing and implementing RDM frameworks.

A number of useful suggestions for improving the frameworks were made. The questionnaire could be enhanced by providing more perspectives on the engagement of end users, research culture, RDM related needs and goals of researchers and broader incentive schemes. The user engagement section could be supplemented with questions beyond technical support. The cookbook provides useful sets of activities for improving RDM, which are consistent with the issues identified by the case studies. The self-assessment tool has high potential for addressing the RDM needs of researchers, but the project team needs to iron out a number of legal and functional issues, and plan carefully to attain a critical mass of users.

Nordic Center of Excellence Justice in Education (JustEd)

JustEd is a joint initiative of the five Nordic countries aiming to address the following question: “How do systems, cultures and actors in education facilitate and constrain justice in the context of the globalising Nordic welfare states?”. Basic data management development relevant to JustEd has taken place in Finland, and is now rolled out to the other groups. The case study involved researchers within the field of social sciences, who mostly work with sensitive, qualitative data.

12 researchers from several JustEd partners answered the researchers questionnaire. The self-reported overall maturity level was 1 out of 8. No suggested activities have been implemented so far, as only a few recommendations were found relevant for the central coordinating unit.

For JustEd researchers the legal and ethical RDM areas are key. A top priority for them is mapping the differences in the national legal frameworks associated with depositing and sharing data in Nordic countries (especially relevant when it comes to comparative and cross-national research). The general impression was that the most important players for improving RDM maturity were the researchers' own institutions and the RDM-related services provided at institutional level.

Overall the case study has been an eye opener that effectively put RDM on the Centre's agenda. Some researchers felt that the questionnaire was less appropriate for social science qualitative research (video, photography, ethnographic interviews, observations), as questions tended to focus on quantitative data assumed to be suitable for open access. The cookbook activities were hands-on and likely to help JustEd improve their RDM maturity. Some recommendations looked more relevant for individual respondents, while others - like those concerning data sharing within a research network - were relevant to the Centre as a whole.

The idea of a self-assessment tool like the one developed by SIM4RDM is very good. Future refinement should aim to make the tool address the needs of researchers in all disciplines. The questionnaire language could be improved, and a number of suggestions concerning specific questions have been communicated to the project team.

Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences

The Hungarian case study focused on improving the efficiency of open access (OA) to scientific publications. The Hungarian Academy of Sciences has recently adopted an OA policy concerning research publications. Their Library and Information Centre maintains a National Scientific Bibliography Database that tracks Hungarian research publications. The Library plans to implement a software tool to expand the capability of this database (record OA status of research outputs, visualize OA statistics by researcher and by research institution), provide statistics on OA compliance, and ultimately increase OA awareness at local and national levels.

The case study focused mainly on technical issues, with a particular interest in open standards and sustainability. The funder questionnaire was tested, with special reference to technical implementation and user engagement. The overall RDM maturity was estimated at below 1 on a scale of 8, which reflects the fact that RDM is hardly a priority for the Hungarian scientific budget. In addition to testing the questionnaire, the functionality of the database was enhanced to enable OA availability handling and provide scientists with information about OA performance statistics.

In spite of a number of issues encountered when testing the framework, involvement in the case study was considered extremely useful. Researchers found that the most relevant correlation of cookbook activities across stakeholders was in the area of open data formats. Other relevant areas for cross-stakeholder activity included DM policy, depositing datasets, and DM standards. Some respondents found it difficult to understand parts of the questionnaire, and were not familiar with

specific terms, such as ORCID. The Library suggested supplementing the cookbook with activities for monitoring RDM compliance by funding organizations.

A number of interviews with high-level research managers were also conducted as part of this case study. Some respondents suggested that projects addressing questions of scientific information in Europe are often tuned to the needs of "western states". In Central and Eastern Europe financial resources are needed for digitization in the first place, and questions of data management, data exposure, data organization can only be addressed afterwards.

Next steps

While developing of the SIM4RDM framework and cookbook, it appeared that the information within the framework would lend itself to an online self-assessment tool. This tool would allow funders, infrastructure providers, institutions, publishers and researchers to evaluate and improve their RDM performance. Users would get benchmarked maturity levels and detailed visualisations of their results in five key RDM areas (organizational, legal, technical, user-experience, data reuse) to help them decide what specific aspects they need to improve. Based on these results, users would be recommended sets of concrete actions and online resources available to help them improve their RDM maturity.

The project has built a functional demonstration of such a tool which will be presented for testing and initial feedback at the RDA Plenary. We are currently in discussions with various partners for future development of the tool and the deployment and maintenance on a managed service.

Envisaged features of the tool include:

- Enable users to identify partners for potential RDM collaboration and follow-on actions, based on built-in correlations of common cookbook recommendations;
- Provide a mechanism for users to monitor the progress and effectiveness of actions undertaken in improving their research data management maturity and processes;
- Enable user feedback on the accuracy of the assessment and the effectiveness of the proposed actions taken to improve research data management, which could be used to supplement the tool's underlying knowledge base;
- Enable new communities to add plug-in assessment criteria and recommendations to the existing knowledge base.

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL

SIM4RDM
SUPPORT INFRASTRUCTURE MODELS
FOR RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

SIM4RDM is an EC-funded project aiming to improve research data management (RDM) policies and practices at institutional, national and European levels. Its vision is to enable researchers to take full advantage of the emerging data infrastructures in the European Research Area by ensuring that they have the knowledge, skills and support infrastructure necessary to adopt effective practices for managing research data.

The project analysed funding programmes and policy interventions that encouraged good research data management, and produced funding and evaluation frameworks and policy recommendations that could be used by various stakeholder groups to improve their data management practices.

Building on the project outputs, an RDM self-assessment tool is currently being developed to help funders, researchers, academic institutions, infrastructure providers and publishers evaluate and improve their RDM practice.

The tool has built-in partner discovery functionality to help users identify other stakeholders who are willing to work together on common RDM issues.

Users select the questionnaire that fits their background, and choose the RDM areas they wish to assess themselves

Users fill in the five sections of the online questionnaire (organizational, legal, technical, user experience, data reuse) by ticking the answer

SIM4RDM Funders Questionnaire

RDMs

Do you provide any activities to encourage researchers to deposit research data in RDMs?

- 1) No, we do not have any activities for this purpose, or for RDMs
- 2) Yes, although there has been some discussion, and we are thinking of it in the future
- 3) Yes, but only occasionally in a few selected programmes, but there is nothing systematic towards depositing RDMs
- 4) Yes, but in some programmes, mainly results are used as an exemplar for other researchers
- 5) Yes, because the tool is embedded in a specific online programme, and we have clearly defined processes for managing data, but we do not yet have the correct in place programme when new results come with an institution
- 6) Yes, but in some programmes, and only sometimes in collaboration with an external partner that has been trained in helping to promote the use of data repositories

1 2 3 4 5 6

User results are sent to a web application that saves the results and generates a dashboard with absolute and benchmarked scores and visualisations of results.

The tool is administered via a simple CMS in which the questions, answers, recommended activities and resources can be easily edited

Based on the results, a set of step-by-step actions for improving RDM practice is suggested. These actions are cross-referenced, so that different users who were recommended similar activities can be put in touch for mutual support or joint action.

FUTURE FEATURES

- ➔ More advanced metrics and visualisations of questionnaire results
- ➔ Comparing current results with results from the past to get an idea of RDM improvement over a certain period
- ➔ Improved partner discovery functionality
- ➔ An appropriate channel for providing feedback on the online questionnaire, recommended activities, visualisation of results, in order to improve user engagement and tool functionality

HOW CAN USERS BENEFIT? TWO SCENARIOS

Scenario A: Research Institution A has implemented a rudimentary RDM policy a few years ago. They've heard about other institutions with more advanced policies, but they're not sure how to improve theirs. Having used the self-assessment tool, the overall score gave them an indication of the maturity of their RDM practices, and the charts showed how they were faring compared to other institutions. The list of recommendations, and resources to help them implement these, provided A with the relevant information and necessary confidence to update their RDM policy.

Scenario B: Research group B is struggling with some legal aspects of depositing research data. The self-assessment tool made this even more apparent, as they scored quite low in the legal section of the questionnaire. In addition to the activities suggested for improvement, the tool provided group B with links to background information on legal aspects. The cross-referenced activities also pointed them to previous users who had indicated that they wished to be contacted by other users who were recommended similar activities. One of these former users was an infrastructure provider who had initially also scored low in the legal section, but improved lately and was now looking for researchers willing to test a new functionality of their data repository. Group B got in touch with them, and the two users realised that they could help each other with their specific RDM issues.